

Casualidad Mine

Baños de Alhamilla, Almeria, Spain

(Part I)

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Introduction

In 1998 a close friend from Almeria – Angel Romero – pointed me to a very small mine near Baños de Alhamilla, called Mina Casualidad. From then on this location has fascinated me (CR) and so I began a research project with my co-authors that has taken 20 years to date.

This paper is the result of many visits and analytical investigation into the unusual (and unexpected) mineralogy of this locality in Andalusia.

History (by Miguel Calvo)

The spa known as Baños de Sierra Alhamilla is located in the center of an area with iron ore workings, which in some cases date back to ancient times. In modern times, in the 1870s several claims were registered in the area, but without significant work being carried out initially. The mineralization appeared in two adjacent claims, named Primero de Mayo and Casualidad. The Casualidad claim was registered in 1873 by Francisco Lacasa Felices, obtaining the number 5,387. The title deed was issued by the Civil Governor on September 3, 1874.

A little earlier, the Primero de Mayo claim, number 4,746, had been registered. Although the deposit was located close to the coast, transportation difficulties made it impossible to export the iron ore, so large-scale exploitation had to await the construction of a railway. In 1874, William Dexter Marvel, an entrepreneur from New York, had met the miners of Sierra Alhamilla, and advanced funds to put the mines in operation. In 1879, he acquired through Felipe Barrón the rights over the Riqueza, Casualidad, and

Graciosa claims, planning the construction of a railroad from the mines to the port of Almería, a journey of 17.6 km. The route was quite steep, which required the construction of bridges and the excavation of trenches. The railroad was designed so that in addition to transporting iron ore it could also transport passengers to Baños Sierra Alhamilla, famous for its thermal waters. It started from El Chorrillo, where a sloping ramp from the Casualidad mine was supposed to arrive, and ended at a dock in the port of Almeria. Authorization for the construction was initially granted in June 1880, and after some modifications the final concession was granted in July 1886. The railway was completed in February 1888, although the ramp from the mine and the link to the dock were still missing. In June of the same year ownership of the railway and mines was transferred to George Stone, although claims of an alleged fraud postponed the legal transfer until October of 1890. In November of 1891, ownership was transferred to Manuel Francisco Requena, and in December of the same year to the English company

Sierra Alhamilla mining area. Miguel Calvo archive.

The Alamillo and Almeria Railway Co. Ltd, which George Stone and Herman CH Borner had created in London immediately before (Gómez Martínez and Coves, 2000). Between the end of 1892 and the middle of 1893, an aerial cable of the Bleichert system was built to replace the previously planned inclined plane. It came into operation in May 1893. The Almería and Alhamilla Railway Company went bankrupt in 1896, although mining and the railroad continued operations on behalf of the creditors. On July 27, 1898, the Sierra Alhamilla Mining Company was formed to exploit the Casualidad, Riqueza, and Graciosa claims. The shares issued did not represent the company as a whole, but each mine had separate shares (Anonymous, 1898). In 1904 the property passed to The Gergal Railway and Mines Co. Ltd, and in 1907 to The Alquife Mines and Railway Co. Ltd. (Gómez Martínez and Coves, 2000).

At that time, the Casualidad concession was owned by the Sociedad Casualidad, based in Almería, and the Primero de Mayo was owned by José Riancho (Anonymous, 1911). As usual in the area, the owners of the mines (individuals or mining companies) leased them to another company in exchange for payment of a fee for the extracted ore, which in this case was 1.5 pesetas per ton (Fábrega, 1909). The Alquife Mines and Railway Co. Ltd. decided to revitalize the mines, conducting drilling and exploration. Up to that moment, some 600,000 tons of oxides had been extracted, without hardly touching the fresh siderite. In the Casualidad mine drilling discovered an area about 10 meters thick rich in complex sulfides of lead and antimony, with a high content of silver, up to 12.35 kg per ton of ore, which was concentrated by washing to up to 115.3 kg of silver per ton. These minerals were disseminated in the siderite and in the shales (Guardiola and Sierra, 1926).

The prospecting shaft that was sunk to investigate this area found abundant water, and the work to drain it caused a large decrease in the flow of the spring that supplied the Sierra Alhamilla spa, so the Civil Governor, giving more importance to the spa than to the mines, ordered the cessation of the drainage work and deepening of the well (Guardiola and Sierra, 1926). The most important extraction of iron ore in the mines of the Baños de Sierra Alhamilla area took place at the end of the 19th century and in the first two decades of the 20th century.

Western gallery entrance to the Casualidad mine in 1998.
Miguel Calvo photo.

Plan of the Casualidad mine. The distances are in meters.

SECCIÓN POR LA GALERÍA CASUALIDAD

1. Terraplén de la escombrera de labores superiores.—2. Filadíos arcillo-talcosos azules y blancos.—3. Capitas de arcilla.—4. Caliza cavernosa del nivel inferior del triás.—5. Capas de arcilla de pequeño espesor (hasta 5-6 centímetros).—6. Caliza sacaroidea cristalina.—7. Pizarras estrato-cristalinas metamorizadas, semejantes a pizarras silíceas duras.—8. Pizarras metamorizadas arcillosas del estrato, más blandas que las anteriores.—9. Hematites parda.—10. Arcillas con cloruros y sulfuros de plata y carbonatos de hierro y plata.—11. Argirosa y galena embrozada con arcillas y pizarras metamorizadas de la caja del yacimiento.

Main gallery and shaft of the Casualidad mine.
The distance from the adit up to the shaft is about 70 mts.
Miguel Calvo archive.

Dump of the Casualidad mine.

View from the entrance of the Casualidad mine to the village of Baños de Sierra Alhamilla.

Guardiola and Sierra (1926) estimate that a total of 700,000 tons of ore, almost all oxides, were extracted. In July 1917, the railroad and mines were transferred to The Chorrillo Almeria Railway Co. Ltd, a subsidiary of The Alquife Mines and Railway Co. Ltd. The prohibition of draining the workings, to prevent damage to the spa, made it impossible to exploit the deep zone, containing siderite, although probably its extraction would not have been profitable in any case, and work was finally suspended in 1919. The railroad could not be maintained only by passenger traffic, and in November 1927 it stopped running (Gómez Martínez and Coves, 2000).

Geology

The Sierra de Alhamilla is part of the Betic Cordilleras in southeastern Spain. Permotriassic sediments are in contact with heavily folded higher metamorphosed older metasedimentary rocks (Platt *et al.* 1983). The workings of the Casualidad mine cut through talc-rich shales, cavernous Triassic carbonates with lenses of hematite, which is enriched at the contact to argillaceous shales. These shales hold embedded silver mineralisations (especially miargyrite) and antimony sulfosalts (especially pligionite and semseyite) in a gangue of dolomite, siderite, and barite. Younger crosscutting veinlets are silver-free and show tetrahedrite and stibnite as major ore minerals. The Casualidad mine is situated about 400 meters northeast of the spa known as Baños de Sierra Alhamilla.

Inside the upper level of the Casualidad mine.

Entrance of the Casualidad mine with the dump in front.

Inside the Casualidad mine.

Sierra Alhamilla with Baños de Sierra Alhamilla in front.

Sampling and Analytical Methods

The studied samples were collected during several visits at different locations in the Casualidad mine near Baños de Sierra Alhamilla.

Electron microprobe analyses were carried out using Camebax SX100 at the Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences of the Ludwig Maximilians University, Munich. X-ray powder diffraction data were obtained using a Seifert XRD3300TT diffractometer (Bragg-Brentano) at the Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences of the LMU Munich. SEM-EDS analyses were carried out using Zeiss EVO MA10 SEM with a Bruker EDS detector XFlash 410-M with Quantax 200 software.

Mineralogy

Elements

Sulfur

Native sulfur was found at the Casualidad mine as a product of oxidation of sulfides. It occurs in highly lustrous, translucent and well-developed microcrystals up to 0.5 mm in vugs or on cleavages mostly near or on the sulfides. The colour ranges from white to pale yellow. Native sulfur is frequently seen at the location.

Silver

Native silver could be detected as very tiny wires on the surface of altered andorite, mostly together with younger microscopic galena crystals. It is very small and only visible via SEM*.

SEM picture of native silver wire on andorite.

Native sulfur crystals on a zinkenite crystal. Fov 0.3 mm.

Fig. 1: Folded structure parallel to the horizontal oriented schist. (Flashlight 16 cm in length)

* SEM.- Secondary Electron Image.

**BSE.- Backscattered Electron Image

Sulfides and Sulfosalts

At the Casualidad mine the primary ore minerals were predominantly Pb-Sb-sulfosalts like tetrahedrite, along with pyrite, chalcocopyrite, sphalerite, stibnite, galena, and chalcocite.

Rarer are Ag-bearing minerals like miargyrite, andorite, ramdohrite, acanthite, diaphorite, and others.

All ore minerals were found in irregular lenticular nodules and small veins from one to a few centimeters thickness. The veins are parallel to the schistosity as well as crosscutting the bedding of the host rock. Nodules are less frequent and were also found parallel to the schistosity especially in tectonic folded structures. These folded structures (Fig. 1) were predominantly found at the Casualidad mine where most of the Pb-Sb-sulfosalts were observed. A noticeable enrichment of miargyrite and chalcocite was observed in a lighter and softer (talc-rich) schist host rock. Sb-rich sulfosalts are dominant, primarily pligionite, fülöppite, semseyite, zinkenite and arsen-rich members of the geocronite-jordanite solid solution series.

Fig. 2: Geocronite-jordanite solid solution measurement field projected on the system Pb-As-Sb

Fig 3: Geocronite-jordanite solid solution series with pligionite (BSE** - Picture of polished section #CR1193).

Geocronite - Jordanite

At the Casualidad mine minerals of the entire geocronite-jordanite series are present. (Geocronite is from the Greek, γαῖα, earth). Extensive sampling showed that jordanite is dominant over geocronite, but shows a wide variation from arsen-rich to antimony-rich members. (Fig. 2)

The formula for average geocronite is $Pb_{14.03} (Sb_{4.65} As_{1.61})_{\Sigma=6.26} S_{23}$ and for jordanite is $Pb_{13.73} (As_{5.59} Sb_{0.14})_{\Sigma=5.73} S_{23}$ – (both calculated from electron microprobe analyses).

Geocronite-jordanite crystal group. Fov 1.8 mm.

Fig. 4: Geocronite-jordanite solid solution series with semseyite (BSE - Picture of polished section, #CR1190).

Geocronite-jordanite
crystal 3 mm in length.

Geocronite-jordanite
crystal group.
Fov 2.4 mm.

Geocronite-jordanite
crystal group.
Fov 6 mm.

Paragenesis: Members of the geocronite-jordanite solid solution coexists with veenite, galena, plagionite and semseyite. Pure geocronite especially coexists with veenite and galena. It is striking that plagionite coexists more frequently with geocronite-rich solid solution, as shown in figure 3, whereas semseyite (Fig. 4) more likely coexists with jordanite-rich solid solution. This mineral series builds lead-grey, massive, rounded and irregular grains or nodules up to 3 cm in diameter. Less frequent are well developed and often twinned crystals up to 4 mm.

Veenite

Veenite was first described in 1967 by Jambor from the Madoc deposit, Ontario, Canada.

During our investigation of ore samples via microprobe, 24 measurement results could be assigned to veenite.

At the Casualidad mine all veenite analyses show a very low As content with a maximum of 2.6 wt-% As.

The average value shows a nearly stoichiometric composition. (Fig. 5)

In the original paper of Jambor 1967, the veenite shows a ratio Sb:As of 3:2. Cook & Damian (1997)

describes an As-free veenite from Baia Mare in Romania. The results from Mina Casualidad are very close to those published by Cook & Damian (1997).

The average formula for Casualidad veenite is:

Fig. 5: Analyses of the **veenite-dufrenoyite** solid solution projected on the system Pb-As-Sb (atom%).

Fig. 6: **Veenite** with **geocronite-jordanite** solid solution series and **galena** (BSE-Picture of polished section #CR1206).

Veenite from the Casualidad mine forms intermediate intergrowths with geocronite/jordanite, galena, fülöppite, and plagionite. (Fig. 7)

Veenite cannot be distinguished macroscopically from other sulfosalts.

Plagionite Group

The plagionite group of the lead antimony sulfide minerals plagionite, fülöppite, semseyite and heteromorphite. This group of minerals typically forms grey metallic tabular crystals, which are hard to distinguish individually without analysis. At Mina Casualidad all members of the plagionite group have been identified (see below).

A visual determination between the minerals of the plagionite group is not possible, although at some places in the mine a majority of “fresh” crystals turned out to be semseyite. At another location the vast majority of crystals were confirmed as plagionite, fülöppite was frequent and semseyite very rare. In the lower parts of the mine plagionite and semseyite were frequent, fülöppite was rare. This is just a statistical result, and a determination without chemical or XRD analysis is not possible.

Mineral Name	Nickel-Strunz Index
Fülöppite	2.HC.10a
Heteromorphite	2.HC.10c
Plagionite	2.HC.10b
Semseyite	2.HC.10d

Plagionite

The mineralogist Johann Ludwig Carl Zincken in 1831 described “Ein neues Spiessglanzerz” in blackish-lead-grey crystals from the Jost Christian mine near Wolfsberg in the Harz mountains, Germany.

Gustav Rose (1833) examined this mineral more closely and gave it the name plagionite after the Greek word πλάγιος “plagios” = oblique, “because of the oblique angle of its axes and its oblique form at all”. His brother Heinrich Rose finally carried out the chemical analyses.

At Mina Casualidad plagionite is the most common mineral of the plagionite group. It forms tabular, curved crystals, mostly aggregated into spheres. Rarely found are single crystals which reach a maximum size of 3 mm. Free crystallized, spherical aggregates could be found up to a diameter of 6 mm, ingrown spherical masses up to more than 10 mm.

Samples were characterized by X-ray diffraction and electron microprobe analyses.

Fig. 7: Correlation of the mineral phases **plagionite**, **fülöppite**, **semseyite**, **heteromorphite** and **robinsonite** in the Pb-Sb-S system together with the **plagionite** measurements (in atom%).

The results (n = 112) are plotted in Fig. 7 and show a homogeneous distribution very close to the stoichiometric composition with a slight excess of Sb towards Pb of 1.5 wt% on average.

The measurements further confirm a small amount of arsenic (maximum 1.2 wt%). The average formula calculated from the measurements is:

Paragenesis: Plagionite occurs with most other sulfosalts, but mainly with fülöppite, semseyite, zinkenite, bournonite, andorite and geocronite-jordanite. Flame-shaped intergrowths of plagionite and fülöppite are common (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8: **Plagionite** and **fülöppite**. BSE-Picture of polished section #CR1208.

Typical iridescent **plagionite** crystal of 4 mm in diameter on matrix.

Plagionite crystals with younger **galena** crystals.

Sharp **plagionite** crystal 2.1 mm.

Plagionite crystal group on calcite. Fov 5.2 mm.

Plagionite crystals. Fov 0.8 mm.

Typical curved **plagionite** crystal sphere on baryte crystals. Fov 4.3 mm.

Fülöppite

In 1929, Finály and Koch described a new mineral of the plagionite group found by Bela Fülöpp at the Kereszthey mine near Nagyág, Romania, and named it fülöppite. Fülöppite has been observed at Casualidad though less frequently than plagionite. It forms tabular, curved, lead-grey crystals, mostly aggregated as spheres. These spherical aggregates reach a maximum diameter of 10 mm. Rarely seen are idiomorphic single crystals up to a maximum of 3 mm.

As mentioned, the minerals fülöppite, plagionite, and semseyite visually cannot be distinguished from each other. When preparing samples for analysis, a reddish-brown streak colour seems to be an indicator for fülöppite, whereas plagionite usually show a grey to black streak colour. But this is only an observation and does not replace analysis.

Samples were characterized by X-ray diffraction and their composition measured by electron microprobe analyses.

Correlation of **plagionite**, **fülöppite**, **semseyite**, **heteromorphite**, and **robinsonite** plotted in the Pb-Sb-S system together with the **fülöppite** measurements. (atom %).

Fig. 9: **Fülöppite** (grey) and **zinckenite** (bright). (BSE picture of polished section # CR1037).

The average formula calculated from the measurements (n=104) is: $\text{Pb}_{2.88} (\text{Sb}_{7.84} \text{As}_{0.27})_{\Sigma=8.11} \text{S}_{15}$
 The results are very close to the stoichiometric composition, with a low deficit 1.5 wt% Pb of maximum.
 The measurements further show a maximum 1.3 wt% of As.
 Paragenesis: Fülöppite occurs with most of the other sulfosalts, however mainly with plagiionite.
 BSE (backscattered electron) investigations show fülöppite with coexisting plagiionite and veenite exist and also with zinkenite and twinnite (Fig. 9, fig. 10).

SEM picture of sharp **fülöppite** crystals.

Fig. 10: **Fülöppite** (dark grey) and **twinnite** (light grey). (BSE-Picture of polished section # CR1208).

Spherical **fülöppite** crystal aggregate. Fov 3.8 mm.

Curved **fülöppite** crystal cluster of 3 mm.

Curved **fülöppite** crystal cluster of 3 mm.

Idiomorphic **fülöppite** crystals.
Fov 1.4 mm.

Iridescent **fülöppite** crystal cluster.
Fov 1.6 mm.

Semseyite

Semseyite is the third mineral of the pligionite group found at the Casualidad mine.

The mineral was first described by Jozsef Sandor Krenner in 1881 from the Felsöbánya Mine, Romania, and named after Andor von Semsey.

Semseyite forms, like pligionite and fülöppite, tabular crystals mostly in groups as well as spherical aggregates. It is visually indistinguishable from the other two members of the pligionite group.

In the Casualidad mine, semseyite is much less common than pligionite and fülöppite.

Semseyite was characterized by X-ray diffraction and its chemical composition determined by electron microprobe analyses.

The calculated average formula from 42 measurements is:

Semseyite from the Casualidad mine has a slightly lower lead content compared to the stoichiometric composition, on average - 0.9 wt% Pb, - 0,23 wt% Sb and - 0,03 wt% S.

Considering the As content of up to 2.7 wt%, semseyite from Casualidad is an As-rich semseyite whose average value is nevertheless very close to the stoichiometric composition.

Paragenesis: Similar to the other phases of the pligionite group, semseyite occurs with most other sulfosalts. Close associations with andorite were found. The mineral also coexists with heteromorphite and, together with intergrowths of veenite.

Semseyite crystal cluster in dolomite crystals. Fov 4 mm.

Single **semseyite** crystal 1.4 mm across.

Sharp iridescent **semseyite** crystal cluster with pale brown alteration to **nadorite**.

Heteromorphite

The mineral received its name already in 1849 from Zincken and Rammelsberg who described a compact mineral from Wolfsberg, Harz, Germany, which was chemically identical to the “Federerz” described by Rose in 1826. But the name did not seem to suit the compact variety of the mineral. So they called the mineral heteromorphite (from Greek *ετερος*, *heteros*, “of another kind” and *μορφή*, *morphé* = form, shape). Pisani describes this mineral for the first time in 1876 from the Caspari mine near Arnsberg, Sauerland, Germany. The first morphological description of the heteromorphites comes from Spencer in 1899. He was the first to assign the mineral to the plagionite group. Although heteromorphite worldwide is the most common mineral of the plagionite group, it is only very

rarely found in the Casualidad mine. There it forms greyish-black, blocky, prismatic crystals with a sharp wedge-shaped termination of up to 1 mm in length. The heteromorphite was characterized by X-ray diffraction and its chemical composition measured by electron microprobe analyses.

The calculated average formula from four measurements is:

Fig. 11: Correlation of the mineral phases **plagionite**, **robinsonite**, **launayite**, **heteromorphite**, **veenite** and **semseyite** in the Pb-Sb-S system together with 4 clearly allocated heteromorphite measurements (red dots), (atom %).

Heteromorphite crystals. Fov 1.2 mm.

Sharp *et al.* (2007) published an atomic% ratio of Pb to (Sb + As) of 0.88 for heteromorphite and 0.85 for launayite which corresponds to the values found here (Fig. 11). Most measurements are mixed analyses and indicate intimate intergrowths between the three phases heteromorphite, launayite and veenite.

Paragenesis: Heteromorphite occurs predominantly with pligionite, semseyite and fülöppite but also with Ag-containing phases such as andorite and miargyrite.

More rarely heteromorphite coexists with members of the geocronite-jordanite solid solution series or with semseyite (Fig. 12).

Fig. 12: Heteromorphite (grey) and geocronite-jordanite solid solution series (lighter grey). (BSE-picture of polished section # RH164_1).

Well terminated heteromorphite crystals. Fov 0.3 mm.

Fig. 14: Diagram of the mineral phases twinnite, pligionite, zinckenite and scainiite in the Pb-Sb-S system together with the twinnite measurements (black dots) (atom%). The red dots correspond to the added values of (Sb+As).

Twinnite

Twinnite, the Sb analogue of sartorite, was first described by J.L. Jambor (1967) from the Madoc deposit, Ontario. The mineral was named after both R.M. Thompson, professor of mineralogy at the University of British Columbia, whose surname “Son of Thomas” in Aramaic means “a twin,” but also in reference to the minerals polysynthetic twinning. At the Casualidad mine, twinnite occurs in the form of flame-shaped intergrowths with fülöppite, pligionite, geocronite-jordanite, and sometimes with heteromorphite (Fig. 13).

The mineral was characterized by 38 electron microprobe measurements and its average chemical formula as calculated from the measurements obtained is:

The measured values were graphically processed in the Pb-Sb-S system and show a very narrow homogeneity field close to the theoretical As-free composition of PbSb_2S_4 . Considering the very small amounts of As, the homogeneity field (red dots) shifts very close to the point of its theoretical stoichiometric composition (Fig. 14).

Fig. 13: Twinnite (grey) and fülöppite (darker grey) with heteromorphite (bright). (BSE image of polished section of #CR1208).

Twinnite from the Casualidad mine has an average content of 0.83 (+/- 0.18) wt% As. Its Pb content (37.4 wt%), is slightly lower than in Madoc (41 wt%) but close to the value of material from Novoye, Kyrgyzstan, measured at 38.7 wt%.

Twinnit from Casualidad mine is not visually recognizable.

Launayite

J.L. Jambor in 1967 described a new sulfosalt from Madoc in Ontario, Canada, which could be observed only in polished section. At Madoc it appears together with veenite and boulangerite. It was named after the French geologist Louis de Launay (1860-1938). Similar to Madoc, the launayite from the Casualidad mine could only be observed in polished section. Its crystal chemical composition was determined by the electron microprobe analysis and the average formula was calculated as:

Only a few measured values (n = 5) could be clearly assigned to the mineral phase launayite, since the mineral occurs in the form of intimate intergrowths with heteromorphite and veenite.

The ratio of Pb to (Sb + As) is 0.85 and corresponds to the literature values (Sharp *et al.*, 2007).

Paragenesis: Launayite coexists with plagionite (Fig. 15) and twinnite.

Fig. 15: **Launayite** (light grey) with **plagionite** (grey) and **twinnite** (dark grey). (BSE image of polished section #RH166).

Robinsonite

In 1952, Berry *et al.* described a new mineral that had already been synthesized in 1947 by the Canadian mineralogy professor Stephen Clive Robinson (1911-1981), and named it robinsonite.

Type locality for robinsonite is the Red Bird mine, Pershing County, Nevada, USA. The type material

had already been found in 1943 by Edgar H. Bailey but only Robinson's synthesis in 1947 made the identification possible.

Electron microprobe measurements on samples from the Casualidad mine confirmed the presence of robinsonite in the deposit as intimate fine-grained intergrowths with plagionite.

The measurements gave a Pb to (Sb + As) ratio with an average of 0.652, which is somewhat lower than the expected value of 0.67 for robinsonite (Sharp *et al.*, 2007). The average crystal chemical formula was calculated from 28 measurements:

Paragenesis: Robinsonite coexists with plagionite, semseyite and members of the geocronite-jordanite solid solution series (Fig. 16).

Fig. 16: **Robinsonite-plagionite** epitaxy (dark grey) with **semseyite** (grey) and **geocronite-jordanite** (light grey). (BSE image of polished section #CR1193).

Zinckenite

In 1925 the mineralogist Johann Carl Ludwig Zincken first described an unknown mineral from Wolfsberg in the Harz Mountains, Germany, which he handed over to Gustav Rose for analysis. In 1926 Gustav Rose examined this new mineral more closely and finally named it after its discoverer Zincken. Zincken himself did not spell his name consistently, so Gustav Rose named the mineral zinckenite and this spelling has commonly been adopted. Rose describes the mineral as a columnar, hexagonal prism sitting on quartz, which are aggregated into groups. Also as thin needle like or fibrous crystals. Zinckenite crystals often show strong longitudinal striations. Both the color and steak color are steel grey. Rose determined a hardness of 3-3.5. Zinckenite from the Casualidad mine forms long-prismatic, needle-shaped crystals up to 1cm in length,

which are usually aggregated into groups or filling small cavities. The mineral is associated with plagionite, fülöppit, veenite, andorite, miargyrit and bournonite. Casualidad zinkenite was characterized by X-ray analysis and its crystal chemical composition was determined by electron microprobe analysis.

The calculated average formula is:

which is near the stoichiometric composition of zinkenite (Fig. 17)

Zinkenite from Casualidad mine has an average content of 34.42 wt.% Pb which corresponds to the literature values of Wolfsberg, Harz (34.33 wt.% Pb). With an average value of 44.11 wt.% Sb, the measured value is 1.4 wt.% lower than that of synthetic $\text{Pb}_9\text{Sb}_{22}\text{S}_{42}$. Zinkenite from the Casualidad mine also contains an average 1.04 wt% of As which compensates the lower antimony content.

In contrast to the previously discussed Pb-Sb-S sulfosalts, zinkenite also contains small amounts of Cu (0.56 wt%), Au (0.30 wt%) and Ag (0.24 wt%).

Pargenesis: Zinkenite also co-exists with fülöppit and plagionite as can be seen in the BSE image of the polished section in Fig. 18.

Zinkenite crystal aggregate in a vug of **plagionite** ore matrix. Fov 9 mm.

Fig. 17: Correlation of **zinkenite** in the PbSb-S system showing the **zinkenite** measurements (in atom%).

Fig. 18: **Zinkenite** (light grey) with **plagionite** (grey) and **fülöppite** (dark grey). (BSE picture of polished section #RH166_3).

Zinkenite crystals with a single native **sulfur** crystal on top. Fov 1.7 mm.

Long prismatic **zinkenite** crystals with **plagioclase** and white **lanarkite** microcrystals on the surface. Fov 3.2 mm.

Sharp prismatic **zinkenite** crystals on **plagioclase**. Fov 2.6 mm.

Perfectly terminated **zinkenite**. Fov 0.4 mm.

Zinkenite crystal group in a vug of **plagioclase-füloppe** ore matrix. Fov 14 mm.

Chalcostibite

Based on its composition Zincken named a newly discovered and described mineral from Graf Jost Christian mine near Wolfsberg, Harz, Germany, as “Kupferantimonglanz” (Zincken, J.L.C. 1835). Glockner translated the name “Kupferantimonglanz” in his mineral systematics written in Latin to “chalcostibites”, a word combination of the Greek words for copper χαλκός “chalkos” and στίβι “stibi” for antimony. (Glockner, E.F., 1847). The anglicized name chalcostibite has since been valid and in general use for this mineral phase.

Chalcostibite at the Casualidad mine rarely forms, free-standing, tabular and low faced crystals up to 8 mm in cavities. More frequent are ingrown and well-formed crystals up to 15 mm in length as well as large crystalline aggregates several centimeters in diameter intergrown in host rock. They are easily recognizable by their perfect cleavage and typical black-grey colour.

Chalcostibite was characterized by X-ray analysis and its crystal chemical composition was determined electron microprobe analysis (n=107).

The calculated average formula is:

This is very close to the stoichiometric value for chalcostibite (CuSbS_2).

Chalcostibite from the Casualidad mine contains an average 0.86 wt% of As and 0.16 wt% Ag.

Remarkable is that chalcostibite from the Casualidad mine also contains an average 0.36 wt% bismuth (with a local maximum of up to 6.2 wt%). This element otherwise is extremely rare at this mine.

Paragenesis: Chalcostibite, bournonite, tetrahedrite, miargyrite, and andorite occur associated with each other as can be seen by BSE images of polished sections (Fig. 19 – 21).

Close and partly oriented intergrowths of chalcostibite with miargyrite and bournonite are relatively common.

Fig. 19: **Chalcostibite** (dark grey) with **bournonite** (light grey) and **miargyrite** (grey). (BSE picture of polished section #CR1196).

Fig. 20: **Chalcostibite** (dark grey) with **bournonite** (grey) and **andorite** (light grey) (BSE picture of polished section #CR1199).

Fig. 21: **Chalcostibite** (grey) with **bournonite** (light grey) and **tetrahedrite** (dark grey). (BSE picture of polished section #CR1033).

Chalcostibite crystal in calcite matrix. Fov 8 mm. Carlos Utrera Martin coll.

Chalcostibite crystal on tetrahedrite ore. Fov 8 mm.
Carlos Utrera Martin coll.

Chalcostibite crystal 8 mm in size.

Chalcostibite crystal on tetrahedrite ore. Fov 8 mm.
Carlos Utrera Martin coll.

Chalcostibite crystal associated with tabular andorite crystals. Fov 6.4 mm.

Bournonite

Back in 1797, Philip Rashleigh described a mineral from Cornwall, which was studied and described more closely in 1804 by Jacques Louis Count de Bourbon, a French mineralogist and crystallographer. In 1805, Robert Jameson named the mineral bournonite in his honor (Hatchett, 1804, and Jameson, 1805). Bournonite at the Casualidad mine relatively frequent was found at different sites in the form of tiny crystals on tetrahedrite. Very rarely beautiful cogwheel shaped crystals up to 5 mm were found. In addition to massive intergrown ore nodules up to 1 cm in diameter, the mineral occasionally also forms freestanding prismatic or tabular crystals up to 5 mm in cavities. Often the mineral is, at least superficially, altered into “bindheimite”.

The mineral was first identified by its typical morphology and subsequently characterized by X-ray analysis.

Its exact chemical composition was determined by microprobe measurements (n = 30).

The Casualidad bournonite shows a low content of 0.38 wt.% As and 0.1 wt.% Ag. The calculated average formula is: $Pb_{1.01} Cu_{1.01} (Sb_{1.05} As_{0.03})_{\Sigma=1.08} S_3$ close the theoretical, stoichiometric composition.

Paragenesis: Bournonite occurs associated with most other Sb sulfosalts such as plagiornite, fülöppite, semseyite, veenite, heteromorphite, and zinkenite.

The mineral is also associated with the miargyrite and andorite, as well as with tetrahedrite and chalcostibite.

Coexistence with chalcostibite, miargyrite, tetrahedrite, or andorite is frequently observed in polished sections. (Figs. 22 – 23).

Fig. 22: **Bournonite** (light grey) with **miargyrite** (grey) and **chalcostibite** (dark grey). (BSE picture of polished section #CR1199).

Cogwheel shaped **bournonite** crystal cluster of 12 mm.

Bournonite crystals on **andorite**. BSE picture.

Fig. 23: **Bournonite** (light grey) with **andorite** (grey), **chalcostibite** (dark) and **miargyrite** (dark grey). (BSE picture of polished section #CR1199).

Cogwheel shaped **bournonite** crystal cluster of 12 mm.

Bournonite crystal on **tetrahedrite** with blue **chalcantite**. Fov 0.8 mm.

Sharp **bournonite** crystal cluster of 4.2 mm size.

Bournonite crystal group. Fov 3.2 mm.

Tetrahedrite

In 1845, Wilhelm von Haidinger named the mineral, formerly known as “Fahlerz”, for its frequent tetrahedral habit, tetrahedrite (Haidinger 1845). Tetrahedrite is the most abundant sulfosalt at the Casualdad mine. It occurs at many sites in the mine, in two differing parageneses. Frequently the mineral occurs in the form of small crystalline veins up to several centimeters thickness, in open spaces including some well developed and multi-faced crystals. Only the sulfides bournonite and stibnite as well as numerous secondary formations, predominantly atacamite, can be found in this paragenesis. Secondly, tetrahedrite is found in close paragenesis with silver sulfosalts such as miargyrite and andorite. According to their paragenesis, the two tetrahedrite phases differ substantially in their crystal chemical composition. Samples from the silver sulfosalt-free paragenesis were characterized by X-ray analysis and electron

Fig. 24: Graphical representation of the measured data ($n=39$) in the (Cu, Fe, Ag, Zn)-(Sb, As)-S system in relation to the theoretical composition of **tetrahedrite** $(\text{Cu, Fe, Ag, Zn})_{12}(\text{Sb, As})_4\text{S}_{13}$ (red dot, in atom%).

microprobe measurements (n = 39), from which the following average formula for this type of tetrahedrite could be calculated:

The measured values show a very narrow homogeneity field around the theoretical point of the stoichiometric composition of tetrahedrite; with the formula $(\text{Cu}, \text{Fe}, \text{Ag}, \text{Zn})_{12} \text{Sb}_4 \text{As}_{13}$ (Fig. 24).

Tetrahedrite from the paragenesis with silver sulfosalts, which we will here call tetrahedrite-Ag, was characterized by x-ray diffraction. Measurements by electron microprobe (n = 31), yielded the following average formula for tetrahedrite-Ag: $(\text{Cu}_{7.99} \text{Fe}_{1.38} \text{Ag}_{2.7} \text{Zn}_{0.67})_{\Sigma} = 12.74 (\text{Sb}_{3.73} \text{As}_{0.72})_{\Sigma} = 4.45 \text{S}_{13}$

The different contents of the different elements vary as follows: Cu 24.6-30.6 wt%, Fe 2.2 - 5.2 wt%, Ag 11.7-17.4 wt% and Zn 1.4 - 4.5 wt%.

With an average of 2.9 wt.% As, the sulfosalt also contains small amounts of arsenic.

Remarkable is the high Zn-content of some of the samples.

Fig. 25: Graphical representation of the measured data of the **silver-rich tetrahedrite** (n=31) in the (Cu,Fe,Ag,Zn)-(Sp,As)-S system in relation to the theoretical composition of **tetrahedrite** $(\text{Cu}, \text{Fe}, \text{Ag}, \text{Zn})_{12} (\text{Sb}, \text{As})_4 \text{S}_{13}$ (red dot, in atom%).

Fig. 26: **Tetrahedrite** with **bournonite** and **chalcocite**. (BSE picture of polished section CR1049).

Fig. 27: **Tetrahedrite** (dark grey) with **miargyrite** (grey). (BSE image of polished section CR1196).

Tetrahedrite crystals with small **atacamite** crystals and white gypsum. Fov 2.2 mm.

Tetrahedrite crystal cluster with white dolomite-magnesite crystals. Fov 14 mm.

Paragenesis: Tetrahedrite has been found very frequently coexisting with bournonite, stibnite, chalcopyrite, and chalcostibite. (Fig. 26). Tetrahedrite-Ag on the other hand only does coexist with miargyrite and andorite. (Fig. 27).

Stibnite

Stibnite has been known for more than 5,000 years and was at first mainly used in lightly adhering cosmetics, spreading rapidly throughout the Orient and Africa. Stibnite is also cited as eyeshadow in the Bible and was used as medicine in the past. Paracelsus already used the so-called “Antimonium praecipitatum” in tonics and rejuvenating agents as well as a vulnerary drug (Jungbluth-Opota, 2007).

The name “stibnite”, which is commonly used today,

Tetrahedrite crystals with thin layer of chalcopyrite. Fov 1.3 mm.

Iridescent stibnite crystals. Fov 2.4 mm.

derives from the Latin “stibium” but also from the Greek στιβι “stibi”, στιμμυ “stimmi”, and Πλατνόθαλμου the name for a black mineral powder.

Beudant introduced the name “Stibine” in 1832 before Dana changed it to stibnite in 1854. (Spencer, 1937).

At the Casualidad mine stibnite is predominantly found on or close to tetrahedrite, but could also be found in small cavities lined with dolomite-magnesite solid solution crystals as small sprays or bi-terminated, short prismatic crystals up to 3 mm.

Very rarely stibnite displays prismatic crystals with short needle-like extensions (similar to ramdohrite).

Frequently the mineral is superficially altered with white coatings up to completely converted crystals.

Biterminated stibnite crystals. Fov 21 mm.

Superficially altered stibnite crystals with blue connellite-buttenbachite aggregates. Fov 1.8 mm.

Stibnite is found together with almost all described sulfosalts. After tetrahedrite it is the most widespread sulfide at the Casualidad mine.

Stibnite was characterized by X-ray analysis and its composition was determined by microprobe measurements (n = 18). From this we can calculate the following formula for stibnite from Casualidad mine:

Again, the measurements show a homogeneous distribution very close to the theoretical point of the stoichiometric composition of stibnite with the formula Sb_2S_3

Paragenesis: Stibnite occurs with andorite and bournonite and also with miargyrite.

Sometimes it can be difficult to differentiate between stibnite and andorite which appears in a similar morphology. To look at the paragenesis can be helpful. Andorite is only found with other Ag-bearing sulfosalts – mostly miargyrite, whereas stibnite is predominantly associated with tetrahedrite.

Galena
crystal, 1
mm across.

Blue iridescent **covellite** aggregates with **zinkenite** needle covered by a white oxidation product - probably lanarkite - and blocky bournonite crystals. The hair-like white mineral is gypsum.

Galena

Already the Roman scientist Plinius the Elder (23-79AD) used the term “galena” for the mineral mined as “Glanz”. The miner’s term “Glanz” for the lead ore has been documented since the 16th century, but later it became the general collective name for all shiny metallic sulfide ores. Abraham Gottlob Werner (1749-1817) embossed the term “Bleiglanz” to differentiate between the metallic sulfide ores. Since about 1850, the term galena is generally used. (Lüschen, 1979)
At the Casualidad mine, galena forms tiny black-grey grains mostly closely associated with Sb sulfosalts such as pligionite and semseyite. Significantly rarer are small octahedral and often twinned crystals to 2 mm. These are always found in association with crystals of the jordanite-geocronite solution series. The mineral was characterized by X-ray analysis and its composition was determined by microprobe measurements (n = 31). The measurement results show a very low, nonstoichiometric excess of Pb as well as small amounts of antimony (Ø 0.5 wt%) and traces of silver (Ø 0.1 wt %) and arsenic (Ø 0.1 wt%).
Paragenesis: Galena coexists with members of the jordanite-geocronite solution series, veinite and semseyite.

Covellite

In 1815, Johann Carl Freiesleben first described a new copper ore of a glaze-blue colour, and 17 years later, Beudant provided the current name covellite for this new copper ore. (Freiesleben 1815, Beudant 1832).

As a typical alteration product of tetrahedrite, covellite appears at the Casualdad mine as tiny, blue-black flaky or earthy coatings on tetrahedrite, chalcostibite and other sulfosalts.

Less common are small, thin hexagonal blades (mostly close to tetrahedrite), or needle-like pseudomorphs. The mineral was characterized by XRD and EDS and appears at all tetrahedrite-bearing sites.

Sphalerite

The name sphalerite derives from the Greek “sphaleros” = insidious, since sphalerite had similar physical properties to metal ores, but it was not until the 18th century that a metal could be obtained from it. Recognition as a zinc ore came in 1735 (Lüschen, 1979). At the Casualdad mine sphalerite occurs very rarely in the form of black-brown grains up to about 10 mm diameter.

Paragenesis: With Sb sulfosalts such as plagionite and fülöppite. It could also be detected very rarely as tiny crystals on plagionite (possibly a secondary formation). Sphalerite was characterized by XRD, EDS and microprobe.

Chalcopyrite crystals on dolomite-magnesite crystals. Fov 1.2 mm.

SEM picture of **sphalerite** crystals on a **plagionite** crystal, with zinkenite needles.

Pyrite

Pyrite has been known to humanity since the Stone Age. The name derives from the Greek “pyros” meaning fire, and refers to the property by which one could produce fire when splinters are knocked off.

At the Casualdad mine Pyrite appears syngenetic and widespread, forming typical cubic to multifaceted, often also striated, red-gold-yellow crystals up to 5 mm across often embedded in the host rock.

Pyrite was characterized by X-ray and its crystal chemical composition determined by microprobe. Paragenesis: Pyrite occurs isolated in gypsum and schist as well as in paragenesis with andorite and miargyrite.

Chalcopyrite

The name chalcopyrite is derived from the Greek words “chalkos” meaning copper and “pyros” fire and was first described in 1725. (Henckel, 1725).

Chalcopyrite occurrences at the Casualdad are quite inconspicuous, and although ubiquitous the mineral is relatively rare.

Chalcopyrite forms small, brass-yellow and partially tarnished, tetragonal crystals up to a maximum of 3 mm, in small cavities of dolomite-magnesite-siderite vugs and as very thin coatings on tetrahedrite crystals (see under tetrahedrite). The mineral was characterized by x-ray.

Christian Rewitzer

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Tomas Fehr (†2014)

Mineral photos: **Christian Rewitzer**

(To be continued in the next issue)

Casualidad mine

Baños de Alhamilla, Almeria, Spain

(Part II)

Christian Rewitzer, Rupert Hochleitner and Thomas Fehr † (2014)

Miargyrite

In his book “Grundriss der Mineralogie” (1824) Friedrich Mohs described a new mineral from Grube Neue Hoffnung in Bräunsdorf, Erzgebirge, Saxony, Germany, which he called “hemiprismatic Ruby Blende” (Mohs, 1824). Heinrich Rose performed a quantitative analysis and first described it as a new mineral in 1829. He proposed a new and shorter name for this mineral, miargyrite, a combination of the Greek ἀργυρος “argyros” for silver and μειων “meion” for less, in reference to the lower silver content compared to pyrargyrite (Rose, 1829). Although the Casualidad mine is still called “Mina de la Plata” by the locals, for a long time we did not find any silver minerals while collecting there. When miargyrite was finally proven, it was the first silver mineral confirmed since the beginning of our study.

The miargyrite exhibits well-formed large, free-standing and multi-faceted crystals, with typical striations, up to 7 mm size, in cavities. Larger crystals (up to 10 mm) were found embedded in the host rock. They attracted attention because of their conchoidal fracture and their red internal reflections under strong light.

It can be easily distinguished by its red to red-brown streak from other accompanying minerals. Miargyrite could be found at only very few sites in the mine.

It was characterized by X-ray investigations and its chemical composition was determined by microprobe measurements (n = 72), giving the following formula:

The measurement results indicate stoichiometric value of AgSbS_2 . Miargyrite from the Casualidad mine contains on average 0.72 wt% of As (maximum 1.5 wt%) and 0.55 wt% of Cu (maximum 1.94 wt%). In a few measurements, it was also possible to detect 0.55 wt% of Au.

Miargyrite occurs with chalcostibite. There are sharp phase boundaries between the two phases and there is no Ag-Cu exchange and thus no phase mixing between miargyrite and chalcostibite (fig 28). This corresponds to the findings published by Harlov (1999) on the Ag-Cu exchange of various sulphosalts. Miargyrite also co-exists with andorite and bournonite (fig. 29) as well as with tetrahedrite (fig. 30) and stibnite (fig. 31). Paragenesis: with andorite, chalcostibite, bournonite, and tetrahedrite; more rarely also with pligionite, fülöppite, or semseyite. Also associated with zinkenite and stibnite as well as with acanthite, ramdohrite, and diaphorite.

Fig 28.- **Miargyrite** (grey) with chalcostibite (dark grey), and bournonite (light grey). (BSE image of polished section CR 1199).

Fig 29.- **Miargyrite** (grey) with andorite (dark grey), bournonite (lighter grey), and chalcostibite (dark grey). (BSE image of polished section CR 1199)

Fig 30.- **Miargyrite** (grey) with tetrahedrite (dark grey), and bournonite (light grey). (BSE image of polished section CR 1196).

Fig 31.- **Miargyrite** (light grey) with stibnite (grey). (BSE image of polished section CR 1018).

SEM image of **miargyrite** crystals.

Typical **miargyrite** crystal group. Fov 8 mm.

Miargyrite crystal. Fov 4 mm.

Miargyrite crystal with a sulphur crystal on top. Fov 2 mm.

Lustrous 5 mm **miargyrite** crystal.

Group of **miargyrite** crystals, 6 mm.

Miargyrite crystal cluster, 12 mm.

Miargyrite-As

Microprobe measurements on some samples showed high levels of arsenic (n = 15). The resulting crystal chemical composition gives the formula:

In fig. 32, the measurement results are shown graphically and show a homogeneity range along the binary miargyrite - smithite. The measurements show a small, non stoichiometric excess of silver. Miscibility between the two phases has not been described so far. Only Effenberger *et al.* (2002) indicates any evidence for a limited solid solution. Effenberger mentions a triclinic phase with the composition AgSbS_2 , in which the ratio of As / (Sb + As) is between 0.08 and 0.28. This ratio is 0.279 (on average) for the present results from the Casualidad mine.

Fig. 32.- Graphical representation of measured data (n=15) in the Ag-Sb-As system in relation to the theoretical composition of miargyrite and smithite (in atom%).

Fig. 33.- Graphical representation of measured data (n=20) in the Ag-Sb-As system in relation to the theoretical composition of ferdowsiite (blue), miargyrite (green) and smithite (orange)(in atom%).

Ferdowsiite

During the investigation of the As-rich miargyrite phase, some measurement points showed a chemical composition very close to that of the newly described mineral ferdowsiite (2013 by Makovicky *et al.*). These grains, included in miargyrite, seldom reached a diameter of more than 10 μm . The graphic shows the distribution of the measured points in the AgSbAs system. The existence of ferdowsiite at the Casualidad mine cannot definitely be confirmed at the moment, further investigations have to be done (fig. 33).

Andorite

Andorite was first found in Felsöbanya (now Baia Sprie) in Romania and described by Krenner (Krenner 1892). Almost at the same time Brögger (1893) described a new mineral from Oruro in Bolivia and named it "Sundtite". A little later in 1895 Stelzner described another new mineral called "Webnerite". In 1897 Prior & Spencer concluded that both "Sundtite" and "Webnerite" were identical to the mineral described by Krenner as andorite. (Prior and Spencer, 1897). Andorite has also been detected at the Casualidad mine.

Fig. 34.- Andorite (grey) with ramdorite (light grey). (BSE image of polished section CR 1199).

Fig. 35.- Andorite (grey) with bournonite (light grey) and chalcostibite (grey). (BSE image of polished section CR 1199).

This is the first time that this mineral was found in Spain. Although a differentiation of andorite into senandorite and quatranderite as a function of their lattice parameters has been studied and published in recent literature (Moelo *et al.*, 1984), the following is for only undifferentiated andorite with the formula of $\text{PbAgSb}_3\text{S}_6$. Andorite from the Casualidad mine appears in 2 different habits. Frequently, the mineral forms prismatic, tabular crystals, usually with distinct striations. They often are well-formed, up to 4 mm long, showing a typical grey-black color, rarely iridescent colors. Twinning is also present. Andorite is also found in the form of short prismatic, thick tabular crystals, which are always aggregated into groups. These often tarnished crystals appear together with other silver sulphosalts and rarely reach more than 2 mm in length. The mineral was characterized by X-ray analysis and its composition was determined by microprobe ($n = 141$). The formula calculated from the results of the measurements is: $\text{Pb}_{1.04} \text{Ag}_{0.98} \text{Cu}_{0.11} (\text{Sb}_{3.17} \text{As}_{0.09})_{\Sigma = 3.26} \text{S}_6$. The measurements show a narrow homogeneity field close to the theoretical, stoichiometric composition of andorite $\text{PbAgSb}_3\text{S}_6$. Like many other sulphosalts, andorite from the Casualidad mine shows a low, non-stoichiometric deficit of 0.9 wt% sulfur (on average). Andorite contains a nonstoichiometric excess of 0.56 wt % Sb due to the high antimony supply in the deposit. The mineral also contains up to 1.1 wt% As and up to 2.0 wt% Cu. In addition Andorite also contains very low amounts of Au (on average 0.2 wt%). Paragenesis: The mineral was found with miargyrite, acanthite, ramdohrite, chalcostibite, bournonite, zinkenite, pligionite, fülöppite, and semseyite.

Andorite crystal, 3 mm.

Andorite crystal group, 3.5 mm.

Fig. 36.- **Andorite** (light grey) with pyrite (dark grey) and chalcostibite (grey). (BSE image of polished section CR 1197).

Andorite crystal cluster. Fov 3.5 mm.

Andorite crystal group, 2.6 mm.

Andorite crystal, 1.6 mm.

Fizélyite

Fizélyite was first described by Krenner and Loczky in 1923 and named after its discoverer, Sándor Fizély, a Hungarian mining engineer. In the Casualidad mine fizélyite could only be detected by X-ray powder diffraction (Samples CR909, CR1300, and CR1357). Fizélyite and ramdohrite are very similar so that a distinction between the two phases is not possible on the basis of their physical properties (Moelo *et al.*, 1984.) Microprobe measurements did not give definitive results for fizélyite, with the measured values situated between ramdohrite and fizélyite (fig. 37) and,

Fig. 37.- Graphical representation of measured data in the Pb-Ag-Sb system in relation to the theoretical composition of fizelyite, ramdohrite, and andorite (in atom%).

Fig. 38.- Graphical representation of the homogeneity field of ramdohrite along the tie-line of fizelyite-ramdohrite in the Pb-Ag-Sb- system.

taking into account all measurements, indicating a possible miscibility of the two phases (fig. 38). Fizélyite was detected together with ramdohrite and andorite and as well as with plagionite and semseyite.

Ramdohrite

Ramdohrite was first described by Friedrich Ahlfeld in 1930 as a new mineral from the “Chocaya la Vieja” mine in Bolivia. Ahlfeld named this mineral in honor of Prof. Paul Ramdohr, University of Heidelberg (Ahlfeld, 1930). Subsequent studies by several authors have shown that ramdohrite is a member of the andorite-fizelyite series (Jambor, 1991). This rarely occurring mineral at the Casualidad mine forms needle-like to lancet-like overgrowths on andorite crystals. Tiny spiny balls of dull grey microcrystals could also be confirmed as ramdohrite. Ramdohrite has so far only been found in a few samples. This is the first time that this mineral was found in Spain. Microprobe measurements on andorite samples produced a series of measurements that differed significantly from previous measurements for andorite. Also some BSE images of andorite showed phases with different back-scattering ability. Further measurements (n = 10) confirmed the composition as ramdohrite, with the formula: $\text{Ag}_{2.98} \text{Pb}_{6.23} \text{Cu}_{0.12} (\text{Sb}_{11.35} \text{As}_{0.41}) \Sigma = 11.76 \text{S}_{24}$ The measured values were plotted in the Pb-Ag-Sb system and show a homogeneity field along the ternary tie-line of fizelyite-ramdohrite-andorite close to the

Fig. 39.- **Andorite** (grey) with ramdohrite rim (light grey) (BSE image of polished section CR 911).

Ramdohrite needles on miargyrite. Fov 4 mm.

Needle-like overgrowths of **ramdohrite** on andorite. Fov 2.1 mm.

Fig. 40.- **Ramdohrite** (light grey) with andorite (grey). (BSE image of polished section CR 910).

Fig. 41.- **Ramdohrite** (light grey) with andorite (grey). (BSE image of polished section CR 909).

Ramdohrite crystals. Fov 1.4 mm.

theoretical point of the stoichiometric composition of ramdohrite, with the formula $Ag_3Pb_6S_{11}S_{24}$
 Ramdohrite from the Casualidad mine also contains 0.79 wt% As, as well as 0.2 wt% Cu and 0.2 wt% Au.
 Paragenesis: ramdohrite was only found in coexistence with andorite and bournonite.

Acanthite cluster with miargyrite microcrystals on top. Fov 1.2 mm.

Acanthite

In “Poggendorff’s Annalen der Physik und Chemie” (1855) the mineralogist Gustav Adolf Kenngott described a new silver mineral, which he called acanthite because of its “pointed, orthorhombic” crystals. The naming was based on the Greek word “akanta” for thorn or spike (God, 1855). Acanthite at the Casualidad mine occurs only occasionally. The mineral forms granular to worm-like, black-grey crystallized aggregates. Even rarer are long prismatic perimorphs with triangular cross-section. This phase always occurs in close paragenesis with other silver sulphosalts such as miargyrite and andorite; but also together with chalcostibite. Acanthite also fills smaller cavities between miargyrite crystals or forms microcrystalline coatings on miargyrite. The mineral was characterized by x-ray diffractometry.

Diaphorite

The Austrian mineralogist Viktor Leopold Ritter von Zepharovich was the first to study in depth the mineral freieslebenite. As part of his research on freieslebenite crystals from Bräunsdorf near Freiberg, and Příbram in Bohemia, he realized that, in addition to freieslebenite, there was another mineral that had the same chemical composition (in his opinion) but differed in specific gravity and crystal system. He called this mineral diaphorite after the Greek word “διάφορα”, “diafora”, difference (Zepharovich, 1871).

As part of the microprobe tests on samples from the Casualidad mine diaphorite was also detected, its presence confirmed by x-ray powder diffraction. So far only very few samples could be found. The mineral shows nearly indistinguishable grains in miargyrite (fig 42).

Dull grey **acanthite** with lustrous miargyrite crystals on top. Fov 4.2 mm.

Acanthite microcrystals on miargyrite. Fov 1.8 mm.

Electron microprobe measurements gave the following formula: $\text{Ag}_{3.12} \text{Pb}_{1.83} (\text{Sb}_{2.86} \text{As}_{0.15})_{\Sigma=3.01} \text{S}_8$. The measured values ($n = 9$) plotted in the Pb-Ag-Sb system show a very narrow homogeneity field very close to the theoretical stoichiometric point of diaphorite with the formula $\text{Ag}_3\text{Pb}_2\text{Sb}_3\text{S}_8$. Diaphorite from the Casualidad mine shows a slight deficit of Sb (Ø 0.7 wt%) which is compensated by an approximately equal amount of As (Ø 0.8 wt%).

Fig. 42.- **Diaphorite** grain (white) in miargyrite (grey). (BSE image of polished section CR 993a).

Fig. 43.- Graphical representation of measured data (n=9) in the Pb-Ag-Sb system in relation to the theoretical composition of diaphorite and freieslebenite (in atom%).

Furthermore, the phase has an average deficit of 2 wt.% Pb and small amounts of Cu (Ø 0.28 wt.%) and Fe (Ø 0.09 wt.%). Paragenesis: diaphorite has only been found with miargyrite.

Freieslebenite

Freieslebenite was first described in 1783 by Jean-Baptiste Louis Romé de l'Isle, who called it "Mine d'antimoine grise tenant argent". In his description, L'Isle focused on the morphology of the crystals with prominent longitudinal striation. Johann Carl Freiesleben described the mineral again in 1817 and renamed it "Schilfglaserz". 1845 Haidinger gave the mineral the contemporary name freieslebenite. During our microprobe investigation on ore samples the sulfosalt freieslebenite was detected. The mineral occurs together with andorite, ramdohrite, and other AgSbS sulphosalts. Macroscopically the phase could not be clearly distinguished but it appeared as grains in fuzzy ramdohrite or andorite needle clusters. From the investigated samples some measurements (n = 11) could be assigned to freieslebenite. Compared to samples from Hiendelaencina, Spain, and Příbram, Czech Republic, the Casualidad mine freieslebenite is Ag-deficient with a maximum of 0.9 wt.% As.

Fig. 44.- **Freieslebenite** grain. (BSE image of polished section CR 1294).

The average value shows a nearly stoichiometric composition. The following formula could be calculated from the measurements:

Pyrostilpnite

Pyrostilpnite was first mentioned in 1827 in the "Jahrbuch für den Berg- und Hüttenmann". In 1932, August Breithaupt described the mineral from Churprinz Friedrich August Erbstollen mine near Freiburg, Germany, and called it "edle Feuerblende". The name pyrostilpnite, which is commonly used today, was introduced by Dana and comes from the Greek terms for fire "πυρ" "pyr" and shine "στίλπνός" "stilpnos" and refers to the colour and luster of the sulfosalt. The sulphosalt pyrostilpnite was detected only very seldomly at the Casualidad mine.

Pyrostilpnite crystal cluster with grey ramdohrite. Fov 1.4 mm.

Pyrostitpnite crystal, 1.1 mm.

Pyrostitpnite hollow crystal, 0.8 mm.

Argentopyrite

When examining ore samples, some pseudo-hexagonal twinned crystals attracted attention. These silver-white to lead grey, sometimes tarnished crystals were EDS analysed and identified as argentopyrite. The maximum crystal size reaches 0.3 mm.

Paragenesis: argentopyrite at the Casualidad mine is always associated with pyrostitpnite and observed only on very limited samples so far.

SEM picture of pyrostitpnite crystals. BSE mode.

SEM picture of argentopyrite crystals. BSE mode.

Typically it forms red to reddish brown subparallel, sheaf-like crystal aggregates, rarely also rhombohedral pseudomorphs up to 1 mm. In the process of EDS measurements on samples, which already stood out for their typical colour, the results could be assigned to the sulfosalt pyrostitpnite. The samples from the Casualidad mine showed a silver-rich pyrostitpnite with up to 3.3 wt.% As. The following formula was calculated from the measured values: $\text{Ag}_{3,39} (\text{Sb}_{0,76} \text{As}_{0,18})_{\Sigma=0,94} \text{S}_3$
Paragenesis: pyrostitpnite occurs together with miargyrite, ramdohrite, andorite, and bournonite.

Argentopyrite microcrystals, 0.2 mm.

Nickelskutterudite crystal cluster in matrix. Fov 4 mm.

Nickelskutterudite

This to date sole nickel sulphide was identified by EDS. It displays tin-white crystals and crystal aggregates up to 5 mm embedded in calcite-dolomite veinlets. A common accessory mineral is whitish to light greenish Mg-rich annabergite.

Halides

Atacamite

Atacamite is a typical oxidation product of Cu- sulphides and is very common at the Casualidad mine. The mineral forms slender prismatic crystals elongated along the c-axis; tabular crystals are often twinned. Atacamite is also found in the form of radiating aggregates or tiny hedgehogs up to a maximum size of 1 mm. The color ranges from emerald-green to black-green. The crystals are mostly translucent with a vitreous to adamantine luster. Paragenesis: atacamite is often seen with tetrahedrite.

Atacamite crystal cluster with dolomite. Fov 0.9 mm.

Paratacamite

Paratacamite forms tiny rhombohedral crystals mostly in globular aggregates and also granular to powdery coatings of a blue-green colour. Paratacamite is not as frequent as atacamite, reaching a maximum size of 1 mm. The mineral was detected at several locations in the mine. A Mg-rich variety of paratacamite is also present at the mine.

Paratacamite microcrystals with gypsum crystals. Fov 1 mm.

Tabular **atacamite** crystals. Fov 0.4 mm.

Paratacamite microcrystals. Fov 2.1 mm.

SEM picture of lathlike **kapellasite** crystals. BSE mode.

Kapellasite

Kapellasite was first described by Krause *et al.* from the Sounion mine No. 19 at Lavrion, Greece.

Pale blue to pale blue-green irregular aggregates of blades or needle-like crystals up to 2 mm proved to be kapellasite. The mineral was verified by XRD and microprobe.

Pale blue **kapellasite** crystal cluster, 3 mm.

Kapellasite crystal cluster, 1.3 mm.

So far the Casualidad mine is only the third location for kapellasite in the world and the first in Spain.

The chemical composition is very close to that of the type material. Kapellasite is very rare at the Casualidad mine. The mineral is sometimes hard to distinguish from serpierite, but the crystals always show a duller appearance and a lesser luster than serpierite.

Paragenesis: serpierite, gordaite, connellite, buttgenbachite, atacamite, and paratacamite.

Gordaite

Schlüter *et al.* described a new mineral in 1997 from the San Francisco mine in the Sierra Gorda, Chile.

The mineral was named after the Sierra Gorda. The presence of gordaite in the Casualidad mine had already been cited by Calvo (2014).

Gordaite is present in the Casualidad mine as colorless flakes associated with serpierite, kapellasite, and fehrite, and as interlocking anhedral plates up to 2 mm across. The crystals are transparent colorless to translucent, pale blue-green with a vitreous to pearly luster and a micaceous appearance. Gordaite is very rare at the Casualidad mine.

Gordaite crystals. Fov 2.2 mm.

Gordaite crystal cluster with pale kapellasite. Fov 2.2 mm.

Connellite-buttgenschachite. Fov 1.4 mm.

SEM picture of **connellite-buttgenschachite** hedgehog on dolomite crystals. BSE mode.

SEM picture of **connellite-buttgenschachite** crystals. BSE mode.

Connellite-buttgenschachite. Fov 3 mm.

Connellite - Buttgenschachite

Connellite was first described in 1850 by Dana and named after the first examiner of the mineral and Professor of Chemistry at St. Andrew's University in Edinburgh, the Scottish chemist Arthur Connell. Connellite is common at the Casualidad mine and forms pale blue to deep blue hedgehog groups up to 1 mm in diameter. Connellite forms a series with buttgenschachite which is also present at the location – but much less frequent.

Connellite-buttgenschachite. Fov 0.7 mm.

Paragenesis: as an oxidation product connellite-buttgenschachite was found in proximity to tetrahedrite at almost all locations in the mine. The mineral is also commonly associated with atacamite, paratacamite, and other copper-bearing secondary minerals.

Nadorite

Nadorite was first described from Djebel Nador, Algeria, and was named after the type locality. At the Casualidad mine nadorite has been observed as a hydrothermal oxidation product of antimony-bearing minerals. Casualidad mine is the first reported location in Spain for nadorite. Paragenesis: nadorite forms cream white spherulitic aggregates on semseyite/plagionite/fülöppite, up to 0.3 mm in diameter. Very seldom seen are pale brown to white altered terminations of semseyite/plagionite/fülöppite.

Altered terminations of pale brown **nadorite** on plagioclase. Fov 0.8 mm.

White spherulitic aggregates of **nadorite** on fülöppite. Fov 0.9 mm.

Boleite

Boleite is a rare PbAgCu-chloride first described in 1891 from the Boleo district in Mexico. At the Casualidad mine it appears rarely as very tiny blue cubes up to 0.05 mm across.

Paragenesis: boleite was found in fractures of the schist matrix close to chalcostibite-miargyrite.

Boleite microcrystals. Fov 0.1 mm.

Boleite microcrystals. Fov 0.15 mm.

Cumengeite

Cumengeite is hard to distinguish from boleite, but is much more common at the Casualidad mine. The species forms tiny cubes to 0.02 mm mostly as groups of hundreds of small, deep blue crystals. Paragenesis: the mineral was found on or close to chalcostibite and directly on bournonite crystals.

SEM picture of **cumengeite** crystals.

SEM picture of **cumengeite** crystals.

Cumengeite crystals. Fov 0.2 mm.

Chlorargyrite

Although the Casualidad mine is very rich in silver sulphides and chloride minerals like atacamite, surprisingly chlorargyrite is very rare at the mine. It has been found only on a very small number of specimens – mostly on altered pligionite close to miargyrite. The mineral forms typical crusts and waxy coatings with drusy surfaces or wax- or horn-like masses of a greyish colour. The maximum size of these chlorargyrite aggregates is 1 mm. Paragenesis: chlorargyrite is associated with covellite, tetrahedrite, pligionite, miargyrite, galena, and native silver.

SEM picture of chlorargyrite crystals. BSE mode.

SEM picture of chlorargyrite crystals. BSE mode.

Cotunnite

Casualidad mine is the third Spanish locality where cotunnite has been confirmed. The mineral forms gemmy clear, skeletal microcrystals to 0.1 mm or granular aggregates next to sideronatrinite and gypsum. This inconspicuous mineral has been found only on very few specimens so far, but is probably more frequent at the mine.

SEM picture of caracolite crystals on fülöppite. BSE mode.

Caracolite

After caracolite was first described from Spain recently (Rewitzer *et al.*, 2018), the mineral species was detected also at the Casualidad mine. Caracolite appears as extremely small, gemmy clear pseudo-hexagonal crystals on pligionite/fülöppite/semseyite. Caracolite was only found on very few specimens so far, possibly because of its very tiny, almost invisible crystals.

Oxides & Hydroxides

Cuprite

Only very few specimens with cuprite have been collected at the Casualidad mine. Mostly the cuprite is covered by malachite or copper chlorides or has

Sharp cuprite crystal with malachite alteration of the surface. Crystal size 1.1 mm.

Deep red **cuprite** crystal of 0.5 mm in gypsum.

been completely altered to malachite. Fresh red cuprite crystals are extremely rare and only resist oxidation when covered with gypsum. Paragenesis: crystals reach a maximum size of 1 mm and are associated with malachite, atacamite, gypsum, spertiniite, and other copper chlorides.

Quartz

Quartz is a part of the siderite – schist gangue and is present in all parts of the mine. Crystals however are infrequent. Those observed reach 5 mm in vugs with siderite or dolomite crystals.

Senarmontite

Senarmontite was first described by J.D. Dana in 1851 in honor of Henri Hureau de Sénarmont, Professor of Mineralogy, School of Mines, Paris. Senarmontite is present at the Casualidad mine as tiny white octahedrons as an oxidation product of pligionite, fülöppite, or semseyite. Paragenesis: octahedra reaching a maximum size of 0.1 mm are associated with pligionite, fülöppite, semseyite, zinkenite, miargyrite, and acanthite.

SEM imag of light grey **senarmontite** octahedra. BSE mode.

Senarmontite microcrystals on pligionite. Fov 0.2 mm.

Tripuhyite

1897 Hussak & Prior described a new antimonite from Tripuhy, Minas Gerais, Brazil, and named it after the type locality. Tripuhyite is rather common within the oxidation zone of the Casualidad. It occurs as radiating aggregates of golden-yellow to yellow-brown needles (pseudomorphous after stibnite) or earthy masses. Paragenesis: stibnite, tetrahedrite, geocronite-jordanite, and pligionite/fülöppite/semseyite.

Tripuhyite crystals on pligionite matrix. Fov 1.4 mm.

Oxyplumboroméite

As an oxidation product of bournonite, oxyplumboroméite is also present at the Casualidad mine; forming mostly massive and cryptocrystalline masses or crusts, reniform masses or nodular aggregates of yellow, yellow-brown or yellow-green dull color. It is rather frequent in the heavily oxidized ore zones of the mine. Paragenesis: with bournonite, pligionite/fülöppite/semseyite, and geocronite-jordanite.

Mopungite

1985 Sid Williams described a new member of the stottite group and named it after its type locality, Mopung Hills in Nevada. Mopungite occurs at the Casualidad mine as a pseudomorph after stibnite. The color is white to cream, sometimes bluish or greenish.

Mopungite crystal group, 1 mm.

These pseudomorphs can reach a maximum crystal size of 1 mm and are associated with tetrahedrite and bournonite. Copper-chlorides are also associated. Mopungite sprays or single crystals are seldom seen at the locality. This is the first time that this mineral has been found in Spain.

Mopungite crystal group on tetrahedrite. Fov 0.7 mm.

Spertiniite

Spertiniite is a rare mineral, first found in a rodingite dyke exposed in the east side of the Jeffrey mine open pit. During our study of the secondary minerals of the Casualidad mine, a deep apple-green, globular mineral

Globular spertiniite partly covered by gypsum. Fov 4 mm.

Deep green spertiniite with cuprite crystal. Fov 1.8 mm.

was noticed; further microprobe and XRD analyses confirmed the presence of spertiniite. Spertiniite forms globular, radial aggregates of a deep apple-green color with a light green core. Most of these botryoidal aggregates were covered with gypsum which was probably the reason why they could resist the environmental influences in the mine. To our knowledge this is the first time that this mineral has been found in Spain. Spertiniite is associated with cuprite and gypsum with only very few specimens found.

Lepidocrocite microcrystals. Fov 0.3 mm.

Goethite

Goethite is frequently seen at the locality in massive or fine grained form, sometimes botryoidal masses or thin veins in the schist.

Lepidocrocite

Lepidocrocite appears rarely as typical bladed, reddish brown to orange-red crystals up to 0.3 mm on siderite veins.

Cervantite

Cervantes in Galicia, Spain, is the type locality of the rare antimony oxide cervantite. This mineral at the Casualidad mine shows crusts of tiny needles on altered stibnite.

The mineral is scarce at the Casualidad mine and can be confused with other, similar looking minerals.

Cervantite rim on tetahedrite. Fov 0.3 mm.

Paragenesis: associated with stibnite, tetrahedrite, and sometimes with secondary copper minerals.

Rosiaite

Rosiaite was first described from Cetine mine, formerly named Rosia mine, Siena, Italy.

At Casualidad the mineral exhibits grey pseudomorphs after stibnite and flaky aggregates on or close to altered stibnite. It has been EDS analyzed.

Rosiaite is very rare at the location and can be confused with other similar looking oxidation products of stibnite.

SEM picture of **rosiaite**.

Ferrinatrinite

During the investigation of the mine straw-yellow acicular balls and sprays within cleavages in the schist were observed. EDS and XRD analysis showed this to be ferrinatrinite. The mineral was only found at one site and only on a few specimens. It forms sprays and acicular balls to 2 mm in diameter consisting of transparent, tabular crystals. No other associated minerals were detected.

Carbonates

Calcite

Calcite is present at the Casualidad mine but not common. It seldom forms good crystals or crystal aggregates in vugs in the ore and siderite nodules. These crystal groups can reach 1 cm in size.

Spherulitic **ferrinatrinite**. Fov 2 mm.

Dolomite - Magnesite

Beautiful saddle-shaped crystals of different colors can be found in cleavages or vugs at all sites in the mine. They were analyzed as a solid solution of dolomite-magnesite colored by small amounts of Cu, Sb or/and Fe. The crystal size can reach 2 mm and internal growth phantoms are frequent.

Transparent **dolomite-magnesite** crystals with typical phantoms. Fov 4 mm.

Aragonite

Aragonite occurs as gemmy white acicular balls of prismatic crystals, acicular along the c-axis. These aggregates can reach 2 mm in diameter and are fairly common in the deposit.

Aragonite hedgehogs of 2 mm.

Silky malachite ball of 0.5 mm in size.

Malachite

At the Casualidad mine malachite forms green sprays and pseudomorphs replacing cuprite (rare). Most of the analyzed and similar looking green examples turned out to be copper-chlorides. Paragenesis: only a few specimens of malachite have been reported – mostly associated with cuprite.

White artinite on andorite crystal. Fov 0.6 mm.

Artinite

Artinite is a typical low-temperature alteration product at the Casualidad mine. It occurs as tiny white spherical aggregates composed of radiating fibers or fibrous crusts. Artinite can be confused with similar looking minerals like chlorartinite, anglesite, hörnesite, and others. The mineral was found rarely in ore veinlets.

Chlorartinite

During the analytical study of artinite the chloride analogue of artinite was also detected. It occurs very similarly to artinite with the only difference that it was sometimes associated with minerals of the atacamite series.

Chlorartinite fibers. Fov 0.4 mm.

Chlorartinite is very rare at the Casualidad mine, the third location in the world where this mineral has been found and the first in Spain.

Cerussite crystal on galena. Crystal size 0.9 mm.

Cerussite

Cerussite is also present at the Casualidad mine though seldom. It forms crusts of tiny and mostly typically twinned crystals on galena. The maximum size of these crystals can reach 0.2 mm and are only visible as grey coatings on galena by the naked eye.

SEM picture of cerussite crystals. BSE mode.

McGuinnessite spherules on tetrahedrite. Fov 1.6 mm.

McGuinnessite

McGuinnessite is a rare mineral from the rosasite group, first reported from the Copper King mine in California. This mineral occurs sparsely as apple-green spherules on tetrahedrite at the Casualidad mine. So far only a very limited number of specimens has been found. McGuinnessite spherules are mostly incomplete, being either hemispherical or flattened out into films along the joint surfaces. The spherules reach a maximum 1 mm in diameter.

SEM picture of carbonate-cyanotrichite crystals. BSE mode.

Carbonate-cyanotrichite

As a very young deposition on the walls at the far end of the mine, carbonate-cyanotrichite forms tiny pale blue globular aggregates and crusts. The mineral is associated with pale green, powdery malachite and gypsum.

Sulphates

Baryte

Baryte is abundant at the Casualidad mine. It appears as a thick gangue of coarsely crystalline masses (up to 20 cm) alongside the ore bearing parts of the mine; and also as small tabular crystals up to 1 cm in vugs close to the Ag-Sb-Pb sulphides.

Transparent baryte crystal on andorite. Fov 4 mm.

Extremely thin anglesite crystals. Fov 0.5 mm.

Anglesite

Anglesite is abundant but only present as very small crystals or crystallized coatings on pligionite/fülöppite/semseyite, galena, and geocronite-jordanite. Very thin tabular, transparent crystals up to 1 mm are common. As a typical product of oxidation, anglesite can be found on many of the altered sulphides as thin coatings of crystals up to 0.01 mm with an adamantine lustre and white to grey color. Anglesite can be confused with lanarkite.

SEM picture of anglesite crystals.

Antlerite

Antlerite is one of the younger mineral phases at the Casualidad mine. It occurs as earthy crusts and fibrous crystallized aggregates of pale green color, mostly on gypsum. It can be confused with other copper chlorides and copper sulphates.

Pale green crystallized crust of **antlerite**. Fov 0.7 mm.

SEM picture of **natrojarosite** crystals. BSE mode.

Pale yellow crystallized crusts of **jarosite**. Fov 0.4 mm.

Jarosite

Not far from its type locality, Jaroso Ravine, Sierra Almagrera, Cuevas del Almanzora, jarosite is found as amber-yellow to brown crusts or coatings in fissures, especially in the highly oxidized parts of the ore veinlets. Jarosite is very common although minute and well developed crystals are infrequently seen.

SEM picture of **plumbojarosite** crystals. BSE mode.

Natrojarosite - Plumbojarosite

A solid solution of natrojarosite and plumbojarosite is also present at the Casualidad mine. Both endmembers have been confirmed by EDS. Optically, both minerals cannot be distinguished from each other nor from jarosite. Both minerals are rare at the locality.

Beaverite

Yellow-brown grains and small coatings were microprobed and identified as beaverite. The species was detected on oxidized pligionite/fülöppite/senseyite and appears as yellow granular coatings

Chalcanthite

As a widespread product of oxidation of Cu sulphides chalcanthite is also frequent at this locality. It appears as typically blue masses or sometimes small crystallized curls close to tetrahedrite. Because of the mostly arid atmosphere in the mine, chalcanthite is stable.

Paragenesis: chalcanthite can be found with antlerite, atacamite, paratacamite, and other Cu-sulphates

Gypsum

Gypsum is abundant at the Casualidad mine. Close to the entrance there is a large vein of curved ram's-horn gypsum crystals. A very young generation of gypsum as fibrous or granular masses on the surface of the galleries is frequent; but also water-clear and perfectly terminated small crystals in vugs within the ore-bearing zones are often observed.

Gypsum crystal, 2 mm.

Bassanite

In contrast to gypsum, bassanite is very rare at the Casualidad mine. It has been found as tiny whitish to yellow lancet-like crystals on pligionite crystals, and identified by x-ray powder diffraction.

Bassanite crystals. Fov 0.4 mm.

Epsomite

Epsomite occurs as crystallized crusts, delicate efflorescences, botryoidal or tiny fibrous to acicular to powdery crusts covering the walls of the galleries within the mine. The mineral is a very young phase and very abundant throughout, but impossible to distinguish from other white sulphates without analytical work.

Hexahydrite

Hexahydrite forms white powdery masses on sulphides and sulphide-bearing schist. Additionally it grows on collection pieces after one or two years of storage.

SEM picture of **epsomite**.

Devilline

Devilline was named in 1864 by Félix Pisani in honor of Henri Étienne Sainte-Claire Deville. He was professor of chemistry at the University of Besançon, France, from 1845-1851, at École Normale Supérieure in Paris from 1851-1859, and at the Sorbonne in 1859-1881. As a rather uncommon oxidation product of Cu sulphides it is seldom present at the Casualidad mine. Devilline forms sub-vitreous to pearly rosettes and crystalline crusts composed of tabular crystals of pale blue to light green-blue color. Paragenesis: devilline is associated with tetrahedrite and sometimes serpierite, from which it is quite hard to distinguish.

Devilline crystals. Fov 0.4 mm.

SEM picture of **ramsbeckite** crystals.

Ramsbeckite

1985 Hodenberg *et al.* described a new Cu-Zn sulphate from Ramsbeck, Sauerland, Germany, and named it after the type locality.

SEM/EDS analyses of very small emerald green euhedral crystals from the Casualidad mine confirmed ramsbeckite for this location. The crystals can reach a maximum size of 0.5 mm and are associated with serpierite, kapellasite, fehrite, gordaite, and gypsum. Ramsbeckite is rare at the Casualidad mine, which is the first locality in Spain for this mineral species.

Ramsbeckite crystals. Fov 0.2 mm.

Crystallized crust of **schulenbergite**. Fov 2 mm.

Schulenbergite

Schulenbergite was first described from the Glücksrad mine near Oberschulenberg in Lower Saxony, Germany, by von Hodgenberg *et al.* in 1984.

In the Casualidad mine schulenbergite forms thin tabular crystals of light green-blue color, mostly clustered in rosettes up to 0.5 mm diameter, associated with atacamite, buttgembachite-connellite, and gypsum. Schulenbergite is rare at the Casualidad mine and it can be confused with the more frequent devilline.

Klebersbergite

Klebersbergite occurs as pale yellow to orange-yellow crusts on stibnite or as pseudomorphs after stibnite in highly oxidized parts of the ore nodules. It can be confused with oxyplumboroméite which is much more common at the locality. This is the first time that this mineral has been found in Spain.

SEM picture of **klebersbergite** pseudomorphs with tabular anglesite crystals on top. BSE mode.

Serpierite

Serpierite is a rare, sky-blue colored hydrated sulphate mineral. It is a member of the devilline group and was first described from the Serpieri mine, Lavrion, Greece. At the Casualidad mine serpierite occurs as sky-blue, fibrous acicular balls and coatings, less commonly as aggregates or sprays of lath-like to acicular microcrystals, elongated on [100] and flattened on {001}.

Acicular ball of **serpierite**. Fov 1 mm.

Serpierite crystal cluster of 0.8 mm.

The color varies from light sky-blue to greenish-blue. Paragenesis: serpierite is associated with fehrite, kapellasite, ramsbeckite, atacamite, and gypsum.

Lanarkite

Lanarkite is less abundant than anglesite and seen only as very small silky, indistinct crystals or crystallized

SEM picture of **lanarkite** crystal cluster.

Hairlike **pickeringite**. Fov 6 mm.

coatings on plagionite/fülöppite/semseyite, galena, and geocronite-jordanite, or close to these sulphides. The mineral has a white color and cannot be distinguished from anglesite without XRD analysis. Sometimes lanarkite alters to anglesite.

Pickeringite

Pickeringite forms matted aggregates of white, hair-like crystals as a very young growth on the gallery walls. It cannot be distinguished from other similar looking sulphate minerals.

Silky fibrous **alunogen** with brown jarosite. Fov 5 mm.

Alunogen

The aluminum-sulphate has been found rarely as white, silky, fibrous aggregates to 3 mm as a very young product of decomposition of heavily oxidized plagionite/semseyite/fülöppite ore. Accompanying minerals are crystals of sulfur and yellow-green alunocopiapite.

Mallestigite

In 1996 a new mineral of the fleischerite group was described by Sima *et al.* and named mallestigite. Mallestigite occurs sparsely as microscopic white needles on plagionite/fülöppite/semseyite. The mineral may be confused with mimetite. The Casualidad mine is the first locality in Spain for this rare mineral.

SEM picture of **mallestigite** crystals.

Brochantite

Typically brochantite is a widespread mineral within oxidation zones of Cu ore deposits, but it is rather rare at the Casualidad mine. The mineral appears as pale blue-green microcrystals to 0.2 mm along with ramsbeckite, kapellasite, serpierite, and fehrite, although it can be confused with tiny atacamite spheres.

Brochantite cluster of 5 mm in size.

Alunocopiapite

Alunocopiapite was SEM-EDS confirmed as pale yellow-green, globular crystal aggregates on schist matrix close to highly oxidized ore nodules. Only a very few specimens have been found so far.

Alunocopiapite crystallized crust, 1.4 mm.

Prof. Dr. Karl Thomas Fehr on the main dump at Casualidad mine in 2006.

Fehrite

The newly approved mineral fehrite (IMA No. 2018-125a) is the magnesium analogue of ktenasite (Schlüter *et al.*, 2019). Till now it has only been found at the type locality, the Casualidad mine. The mineral is named after our late friend and co-author Thomas Fehr who was a member of our Casualidad study group until his untimely death in 2014. The new mineral occurs as turquoise-green radial aggregates of thin lath-like crystals of not more than 200 μm in the longest direction. It is associated with kapellasite, serpierite, and connellite. The visually very similar serpierite is distinguished by its more sky-blue colour without any green tinge.

Fehrite crystals. Fov 1 mm.

Adamite spherules. Fov 1.2 mm.

Arsenates

Adamite

Apple-green and globular crystallized small aggregates in paragenesis with lavendulan were XRD and SEM-EDS analyzed as adamite. The small spherules can reach 1 mm in diameter. Adamite is rare at the Casualidad mine.

Fehrite crystal cluster of 0.4 mm.

Mimetite crystal sprays. Fov 1.8 mm.

Mimetite

Mimetite forms white to cream-colored sprays and groups with an adamantine luster on geocronite-jordanite and galena. These clusters can reach a few mm in diameter but are uncommon. Mimetite can be confused with mallestigitite (which is usually much smaller).

Hörnesite/Manganohörnesite

During the first visits to the mine, small acicular groups had aroused interest; these radiating fibrous aggregates occur in different colors, from cream–white, pale pink, yellow to blue-green. These were microprobed and XRD analyzed and identified as the rare Mg-arsenate hörnesite. Relatively high manganese contents sometimes point to the existence of manganohörnesite, which displays silky white balls and tabular crystals to 1 mm in vugs together with sphalerite and galena. Hörnesite is frequent at several locations in the mine and is associated with tetrahedrite and stibnite. Other oxidation products such as chenevixite, lavendulan, mopungite, and tripuhyite can also be present. The different colors are caused by small amounts of Cu, Mn, Ni, or Sb.

Pale pink hörnesite balls. Fov 3 mm.

Pale green hörnesite with green globular atacamite. Fov 0.7 mm.

Pale pink manganohörnesite with white balls of hörnesite. Fov 1.6 mm.

Hörnesite balls. Fov 1.4 mm.

Grey-green köttigite. Fov 1 mm.

Köttigite

This rare zinc arsenate has been found as radiating or hedgehog-like aggregates up to 2 mm size of white, greenish grey or brownish yellow color. It is very rare and could only be found in paragenesis with sphalerite and galena.

Annabergite

A Mg-rich variety of annabergite has been identified by EDS. It displays white to pale greenish hedgehog-like aggregates up to nearly 1 mm. It is rare, and when found is always near to nickelskutterudite.

Pale greenish, crystallized crust of **annabergite**.
Fov 2 mm.

Chenevixite

Chenevixite is a relatively rare and inconspicuous secondary mineral in oxidized zones of some hydrothermal, polymetallic ore deposits. At the Casualidad mine it was confirmed as olive-green earthy crusts and coatings near tetrahedrite veinlets. Associated minerals are dolomite-magnesite, stibnite, and hörnesite.

Lavendulan

Lavendulan was first described by Breithaupt in 1837 from Annaberg, Erzgebirge, Germany. A re-examination of Breithaupt's type specimen and the crystal structure determination by Giester *et al.* (2007) came to the conclusion that the "type specimen" of lavendulan was a mixture unrelated to present-day lavendulan. At the Casualidad mine lavendulan is a late and frequent mineral developed as botryoidal earthy crusts and infrequently crystallized globular aggregates. Paragenesis; lavendulan is associated with adamite, olivenite, and gypsum. The mineral was found close to or even on tetrahedrite veinlets.

Blue **lavendulan** with pale green olivenite crystals.
Fov 1 mm.

SEM picture of spheroidal **lavendulan**.

SEM picture of spheroidal coating of **cornwallite**.
BSE mode.

Cornwallite

Deep green spheroidal coatings and crusts with a resinous luster were EDS analyzed as cornwallite. Paragenesis: the mineral is associated with serpierite, devilline, and gypsum, and was found only on very few specimens.

Krautite

Krautite had already been detected by Joan Viñals (pers. communication) from the Casualidad mine some years ago. The mineral is probably more common there but because of its inconspicuous appearance it has only been noticed on a limited number of specimens. Krautite forms whitish sprays to 1 mm in diameter on schist matrix.

Krautite crystal cluster, 0.6 mm.

SEM picture of **scorodite**.

Scorodite

Although scorodite is a comparatively common oxidation product of As-bearing minerals, it is very rare at the Casualidad mine. Scorodite builds grey earthy crusts and aggregates on jordanite-geocroronite. Well-developed crystals have not been observed so far.

Rösslerite

Minute white to very pale pink fibrous sprays and balls of small prismatic crystals near jordanite-geocroronite were analyzed and found to be rösslerite. Analysis confirmed the presence of small amounts of Mn (to 5 wt%) which could be responsible for the pale pink colour. Rösslerite is very rare at the Casualidad mine and this is the first time this mineral was reported in Spain.

SEM picture of **rösslerite** sphere. BSE mode.

Hedyphane

White crusts and small balls as oxidation products on different primary ore minerals are quite common at the mine. Various mineral species were confirmed with this habit or similar, and one of the minerals exhibiting this habit is hedyphane. Hedyphane can be found as crusts of very small needles on semseyite and jordanite-geocroronite and in aggregates up to 3 mm in diameter. The mineral is hard to find, and mimetite is much more frequent. These two minerals can not be distinguished from each other without analysis.

SEM picture of **hedyphane** aggregates. BSE mode.

Olivenite

Olivenite was found as small pale green, translucent, prismatic crystals and gemmy balls up to 0.5 mm on matrix in association with lavendulan. Olivenite is considered to be rare at the Casualidad mine.

Green olivenite with blue **lavendulan**. Fov 1 mm.

Silicates

Nacrite

Nacrite has been found as tiny crystals with silky luster, mostly on dolomite-magnesite crystals or filling voids in matrix. The mineral is very inconspicuous but could be found with most of the sulphides, especially galena and sphalerite.

Others

Rock-forming minerals like muscovite, montmorillonite, siderite, and quartz are also present at the Casualidad mine.

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References

- Ahlfeld, F. Ramdohrit, ein neues Mineral aus Bolivien. (1930, 1930) Zentralblatt für Mineralogie, Geologie und Palaöntologie, A., Jg., S. 365-367.
- Anonymus (1911). Catastro Minero. Estadística Minera de España. Año 1909. Consejo de Minería, Madrid. Pag 34.
- Anonymus (1898). Reglamento para el régimen interior y dirección de la Sociedad Minera Sierra Alhambilla, constituida para la explotación de las minas denominadas Casualidad, Riqueza y Graciosa, sitas en Sierra Alhambilla. S.e, s.l. 15 pages.
- Anthony, J. W., *et al.* (1990) Handbook of Mineralogy. Volume I. Elements, Sulphides, Sulphosalts.
- Anthony, J. W., *et al.* (2003) Handbook of Mineralogy, vol. 5. V, Borates, Carbonates, Sulfates. Tucson: Mineral Data Publishing
- Basso R, Lucchetti G, Zefiro L, Palenzona A (1996) Rosiaite, $PbSb_2O_6$, a new mineral from the Cetine mine, Siena, Italy. European Journal of Mineralogy 8, 487-492
- Berry, L. G.; Fahey, J. J.; Bailey, E. H. Robinsonite, a new lead antimony sulphide. American Mineralogist: Journal of Earth and Planetary Materials, 1952, 37. Jg., Nr. 5-6, S. 438-446.
- Birnie R. W, Burnham C. W. (1976) The crystal structure and extent of solid solution of geocronite. American Mineralogist 61, 963-970
- Breithaupt J. F. A. (1837) Bestimmung neuer mineralien. 3. Lavendulan. Journal für Praktische Chemie 10, 505-5
- Calvo, M. (2014). Minerale y Minas de España. Vol. VI. Sulfatos (Seleniatis, Teluratos), Cromatos, Molibdatos y Wolframatos. Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros de Minas de Madrid. Fundación Gómez Pardo. Pag. 531.
- De Finály, I.; Koch, S. (1929) Fülöppite, a new Hungarian mineral of the pligionite-sensseyite group I. Mineralogical Magazine and Journal of the Mineralogical Society, 1929, 22. Jg., Nr. 127, S. 179-184.
- Effenberger, H., *et al.* (2002) The new mineral baumstarkite and a structural reinvestigation of aramayoite and miargyrite. American Mineralogist, 2002, 87. Jg., Nr. 5-6, S. 753-764.
- Erd, R. C., Cesbron, F. P., Goff, F. E., Clark J. R. (1981) Mcguinnessite, a new carbonate from California. The Mineralogical Record 121, 143-147
- Fábrega, P. (2009). Estudio de los criaderos de hierro de Almería. Revista Minera, Metalúrgica y de Ingeniería, 60, 219-222.
- Fanfani, L., *et al.* (1973) The crystal structure of buttgenbachite. Mineralogical Magazine, 39. Jg., Nr. 303, S. 264-270.
- Giester, G., Kolitsch, U., Leverett, P., Turner, P., Williams, P. A. (2007). The crystal structures of lavendulan, sampleite, and a new polymorph of sampleite. European Journal of Mineralogy 19, 75-93
- Grice J D, Gasparrini E (1981) Spertiniite, $Cu(OH)_2$, a new mineral from the Jeffrey mine, Quebec. The Canadian Mineralogist 19, 337-340
- Haidinger, W. von; (1845). Geognostische Uebersichtskarte der Oesterreichischen Monarchie.
- Harlov, D. E. (1999) Ag-Cu exchange equilibria between α -miargyrite, chalcostibite, pyrrargyrite, and high-skinnerite: constraints on Ag-Cu mixing in α -miargyrite and chalcostibite. Mineralogical Magazine, 1999, 63. Jg., Nr. 3, S. 399-399.
- Hibbs, D. E.; Leverett, P.; Williams, P. A. (2003) Connellite-buttenbachite from the Great Australia mine, Cloncurry: a crystal structural formula. Australian journal of mineralogy.
- Hintze, C. (1904): Handbuch der Mineralogie, Band I, 1. Abteilung.- Leipzig, Verl. Veit & Co.
- Hussak E, Prior G T (1897) On tripuhyite, a new antimonate of iron, from Tripuhy, Brazil. Mineralogical Magazine 11, 302-303
- Jambor, J.L. (1969 a): Dadsonite minerals Q and QM), a new lead sulphantimonide.- Mineralogical Magazine 37, 437-441
- Jambor, J. L. (1967) New lead sulfantimonides from Madoc, Ontario; Part 2, Mineral descriptions. The Canadian Mineralogist, 1967, 9. Jg., Nr. 2, S. 191-213.
- Jambor J.L., Dutrizac J.E. (1995) Solid solutions in the annabergite-erythrite-hörsesite synthetic system. The Canadian Mineralogist 33, 1063-1071
- Jambor, J.L. (1969 b): Sulphosalts of the pligionite group.- Mineralogical Magazine 37, 442-446
- Jungbluth-Opota, S. (2007) Einfluss von antimonhaltigen Wecesin-Streupuder auf die Vitalität, O₂-Produktion und die mikrobielle Abtötungskapazität humaner Granulozyten in vitro. Doktorarbeit.
- Kenngott A (1860) Der Hörsesit, ein neues Mineral aus dem Banat. Jahrbuch der Kaiserlich-Königlichen Geologischen Reichsanstalt 11, 10-11
- Krause W, Täuber H. (1992) Zum Kenntnisstand der Minerale Serpierit, Orthoserpierit und Devillin. Aufschluss 43, 1-25
- Leverett P, Reynolds J K, Roper A J, Williams P A (2012) Tripuhyite and schafarzkitite: two of the ultimate sinks for antimony in the natural environment. Mineralogical Magazine 76, 891-902
- Lüschen, Hans. (1968) Die Namen der Steine. Ott Verlag.
- Makovicky, Emil, *et al.* (2013) Ferdowsiite: a new mineral from the Barika ore deposit, Iran. The Canadian Mineralogist, 2013, 51. Jg., Nr. 5, S. 727-734.
- Moëlo, Y.; Makovicky, E.; Karupmoller, S. (1984) New data on the minerals of the andorite series. NEUES JAHRBUCH FÜR MINERALOGIE-MONATSHEFTE, 1984, Nr. 4, S. 175-182.
- Nakai I, Appleman D E (1980) Klebelsbergite, $Sb_4O_4(OH)_2SO_4$: redefined and synthesis. American Mineralogist 65, 499-505
- Pisani F (1864) Sur une nouvelle espèce minérale du Cornouailles, la devilline. Comptes Rendus Hebdomadaires des Séances de l'Académie des Sciences 59, 813-814
- Pisani (1876) Compt. Rend. Oct. 83, 747 (nach HINTZE, 1904)
- Poggendorff, J. Ch.; Wiedemann, E.; Wiedemann, G. H. (1987) Annalen der Physik und Chemie. J.A. Barth.
- Prior, G. T.; Spencer, L. J. (1897) The identity of andorite, sundtite and webnerite. Mineralogical Magazine and Journal of the Mineralogical Society, 1897, 11. Jg., Nr. 53, S. 286-301.
- Rammelsberg, C. (1860) Mineralchem., 70 (nach Hintze, 1904)
- Rewitzer, C., Calvo, M. Hochleitner, R., and Utrera, C. (2018). Cotunnite, caracolite, sideronatriite and other rare secondary minerals in the Ferruginosa mine, Cabo de Palos, Cartagena, Murcia, Spain. Mineral Up, 5 (1), 66-79.
- Rose, Gustav. (1833) Elemente der Krystallographie: nebst einer tabellarischen Uebersicht der Mineralien nach den Krystalformen. ES Mittler
- Sahl K (1970) Zur kristallstruktur von lanarkit, $Pb_2O(SO_4)$. Zeitschrift für Kristallographie 132, 99-117
- Schlüter, J., Malcherek, T., Rewitzer, C., Hochleitner, R., Müller, D. and Günther, A. (2019) Fehrite, IMA 2018-125. CNMNC Newsletter No. 52, December 2019, European Journal of Mineralogy, 31, number 5-6
- Sharp, W. E.; Wieland, M.; Mittwede, S. K. (2007) A Mineralogical Note on Boulangerite, Geocronite and Yenerite From Near Işık Dağı (Kızılcahamam-Ankara), Turkey. Turkish Journal of Earth Sciences, 2007, 16. Jg., Nr. 1, S. 109-116.
- Sima I (1998) Mallestigit, $Pb_3Sb(SO_4)(AsO_3)(OH)_6 \cdot 3H_2O$, Ein neues Mineral von einer Halde des ehemaligen Cu-Pb-Zn-Bergbaues NW des Mallestiger Mittagkogels in den Westkarawanken, Kärnten, Österreich. Mitteilungen der Österreichischen Mineralogischen Gesellschaft 143, 225-227
- Sima, I., Ettinger, K., Koppelhuber-Bitschnau, B., Taucher, J. & Walter, F. (1996): $Pb_3Sb(OH)_6(AsO_4)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$, ein neues Mineral isotyp mit Fleischerit. Mitt. Österr. Mineral. Ges. 141, 224-225
- Spencer (1899) Min. Soc. London 12, 57 (nach Hintze, 1904)
- Vergasova L P, Filatov S K, Serafimova E. K, Sergeeva S. V. (1998) Chlorartinite — the new mineral from exhalations of the great fissure Tolbachik eruption. Zapiski Vserossijskogo Mineralogicheskogo Obshchestva 127, issue 2, 55-59
- von Hodenberg R, Krause W, Schnorrer-Köhler G, Täuber H (1985) Ramsbeckite, $(Cu,Zn)_7(SO_4)_2(OH)_{10} \cdot 5H_2O$, a new mineral. Neues Jahrbuch für Mineralogie, Monatshefte 1985, 550-556
- Williams S A (1985) Mopungite a new mineral from Nevada. The Mineralogical Record 16, 73-74
- Witzke, T. (1999): Mineralersterbeschreibungen aus Sachsen-Anhalt.- Beiträge zur Mineralogie und Geologie von Sachsen-Anhalt. Aufschluss, Sonderband, 223-249
- Zincken, C. & Rammelsberg, C. (1849): Beiträge zur Kenntniss der Mineralien des Harzes.- Poggendorffs Annalen der Physik und Chemie, 236-267